

The role of space in mathematics education

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Throughout my everyday life as Mathematics teacher I have been thinking about the conditions I put my students through. At some point the question about the role played by 'space' emerged. In this paper, I pursue the conceptualization of 'space' and, in particular, I try to understand the role played by this notion in the development of mathematics education in the remote teaching context. My intention is to conceptualize experiences offered to students based on my own professional context. At first, I explain the context where my question emerged, then I share the comprehension of 'space' I am assuming. I also share a panorama of some research in Mathematics Education, and, finally, I set up some questions to the community, as well as, I set a research agenda.

Forewords

First of all, I conceptualize the difference I am assuming between mathematics education starting with lower case or capital letter. By the latter, I mean the research field, the area of inquiry. By the lower case, I mean the everyday practice of a Mathematics teacher, the actions that take place in relations where the intention is teaching and learning something called Mathematics. In the title and in the scope of this paper, I am referring to the second case.

The main concern here is the category 'space' and how this concept becomes present in the education process, particularly in the teaching of Mathematics. The context is the remote teaching implemented in Brazil during the pandemic. It is not my intention to draw a panorama of the education during this time in this country, but to highlight a case study as exemplary of a kind of situation faced in these days. The situation becomes clearer in the section 'Some exemplary cases'.

As many teachers all around the world, I myself had to deal with some challenges and uncertainty during 2020. The pandemic brought upon humankind a brand-new obstacle for us to face. It is not possible – at least desirable – to list these obstacles as they are the same to everyone. Instead, I picture a scenario where I live to bring some common ground to this argument. Writing about my particular context, in Brazil, this text intends to share some thoughts about the role played by mathematics education in this scenario.

The remote teaching I am referring to was implemented in Brazil in the first semester of 2020. In the institution where I worked during that year, it was implemented in March. It consisted mainly of using Google Classroom to send to students activities covering the content expected in a grade. This was combined with online meetings, in the time when the

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class took place, or at some other time scheduled with students, and also with the use of WhatsApp. In addition, to substitute the live meetings some teachers used recorded video lessons with related tasks, shared in the Classroom, and assisted students following a schedule.

Despite all the efforts to engage students in this remote teaching, each month a greater number of students were late with their activities. Following the situations of these students in the Help Students Service, provided by the institution, I saw that a considerable number were leaving the remote activities to help their families in maintenance duties.

This situation it is not a surprise in itself. Considering the socio-economic conditions in which these students live, it becomes clear that helping the families with the maintenance activities is a duty of the children since a young age. The responsibilities increase as they grow up. At 15 to 17 years old, if they are not at school, they have to take part in the main source of funding of these families. In the next section I present an overview of this scenario.

Some exemplary cases

During 2020 I worked, as Mathematics teacher, in an institution that offers simultaneously technical education – integrated in high school level – and undergraduate courses. The students at high school level have the possibility to live in the campus, while attend two courses: Agroecology or Farming, both full-time – because they have to cover the national standards to the high school level in half-period and attend technical training in the other half. Because of the possibility of living in the campus, many students are attracted from faraway cities and come from very different backgrounds. The accommodation is the main criteria for the final decision of some parents to send their young to the institution – the students are 15 to 17 years old, the legal age in Brazil is 18 years old.

Both courses can be completed in 3 years, if the students pass all curriculum components first time. During this time, the routine of the students starts at 7:30am with breakfast. The classes start at 8:00am and finish at 5:15pm, with 1h15min for lunch at 12:00am. All the meals, including two coffee breaks, are offered without cost. The funding comes from the Federal Government and the agricultural products produced in practical classes are used to complement the meals. This routine begins on Mondays and repeats until Fridays when the students leave the campus and go back to their families during the weekend.

Because of the pandemic situation, students were sent home in the middle of March. After 15 days of interruption in classes, these returned in remote mode as an option to students who wanted to continue their studies. Over the year, while the scenario got worse and worse, the remote classes became mandatory and all were required to return to their studies. This decision added 2 problems in this scenario: (i) It was necessary to think about curriculum adaptation because in the same class there were students following the course since the beginning of remote education and students who started when it became mandatory, and (ii) a number of the students that were not attending the classes, not because they did not want to, but because they did not have the conditions to.

To help the major group of the students that did not have access to the necessary technologies for remote education (e.g., internet access and laptops), the institution started programs to lend mobiles and laptops, as well as offered scholarships that could be exclusively used to pay for mobile internet access. But, these programs could not reach all the students. There was not a sufficient number of devices to meet every request and there were students that live on farms or in villages where there is no mobile signal to access remote classes.

Besides all the technological issues, another concern came to be the relationship with the family. I could refer to the lack of an appropriate place to study, or the absence of support, but the main concern is the social role played by these students. While living in the campus, the young were spared from the work at the family place, a condition that was no longer available during the pandemic time. So, the students had to conciliate a full-time course with some duties in the family place. These duties include, but are not restrict to, taking care of children, attending informal jobs to help the family financially, and dealing with agricultural activities.

It is not surprising – but very concerning – that the rate of students leaving the classes or with results less than expected, was very high. These cases, together with the pedagogical issues related to teaching remotely and concerns about the learning of those students with full possibilities to attend the remote education, put the institution in a very complex position.

Among all these issues I came to understand that the space where these students were living – homes with some level of lockdown, younger siblings and older relatives to care for, duties in maintenance – did not allow remote learning to take place. Engaging these students was not a question about ‘contextualization’. The issue was not to make these students see the Mathematics in their everyday life. As I was realising, the Mathematics became present only when none of these other things were happening. I mean, the education process that in pre-pandemic times was the main concern of these students, in pandemic times, was dropped. It took place only in the time they could save from everyday life activities.

My understanding turned into a concern when as I was reading the Students Support Service report. About one of my 16-year-old student, who was not attending the remote classes, it was written:

[...] a home visit was carried out to understand the situation experienced by the student (father with knee injury that prevents work activities and mother undergoing medical follow-up after cancer treatment). The carrying out of agricultural activities is under the responsibility of the student. They have dairy cattle and all management is divided between him and his younger sister. They report that the internet is shared by a group of residents and they are the last residence and when it is peak time (after 6pm) there is no way to use it, access becomes slow. We suggested printed activities and the student reiterated that he prefers to fail and do it all over again in the next year. He believed that they would return to face-to-face classes soon, and as he accumulated so many activities he did not see the means to resume. (Report about student A).

At this point, it seemed to me that, to this particular student, he had been denied access to the education process. The activities that were proposed by remote education could not fit into the space he was living in. The demands placed by his social relations were not accounted for the scheduled activities; on one hand because he was attending a full-time course, on the other hand because he was no longer living in the campus, but in a space that was not structured around the curriculum. His access to the education process also was denied when the institution insisted on bringing him back to the ongoing process. The reality of this student made claims to other ways of being.

As pointed out by Skovsmose (2005), some learning obstacles are the result of being subject to an absurd policy. I mean, some processes of exclusion can be hidden in the way a policy is dressed up. What else could the remote education be, seen from a perspective based in the everyday life of student A? The 'absurd' is not a characteristic of the remote education in itself, only in contrast with the space where this student lives might one state this value judgement.

This same question could be raised based on 16-year-old student B's report. About him it was written:

There is no internet at home, installing one access point by radio has a very high cost. No cellular network. He lives in the farm zone at 25km from the centre of nearby city. He gets in touch only when he is working at his sister's house (planting onions). He expressed concern about not being promoted to the next grade. I asked about the possibility of contacting the Municipality Education Department of the nearby city to provide space to take the classes, but the student claims that he has a logistical problem, they are without a car and he uses only a motorbike (without license) to get around. I did not feel the willpower on the part of the student to seek a solution to his problem. He knew about the Digital Aid Notice, but he didn't sign up. (Report about student B).

Instead of pursuing a value judgement of remote education, I take the road of asking myself what could a mathematics education do to deal with this matter from a non-colonizing perspective. I mean, how could I analyse this situation without normalizing it. Neither a perspective centred in institutional curriculum and a formal process of education that blames the student, nor an everyday life-based perspective that denies the values of a formal education.

My concern might be formulated in these following questions: How does education occupy the space that children and families live in? How does everyday life make itself present in the education process of these children? What is the relation between education and space? It is in response to this last one, that I wrote this paper.

Milton Santos' concept of space

Milton Santos was a Brazilian thinker, very important to the Geography field. His work has become relevant in different research areas. His is best known for his theorization around Space and Territory. As a researcher he went beyond theorization about 'oppressive political economic and colonial relations that have shaped Brazil. Within his writings and practices

he also, crucially, fought for and found promise in counter-rational, non-hegemonic values and knowledges placed at risk by global capital.' (Melgaço & Prouse, 2017, p. 2).

The notion of 'space' raised in Santos' work involves at the same time the form (the objects in the space), the function of these objects (the action that takes place in relations to that objects), and the structure (the social movement around those objects), that is, Santos' proposal is to understand space as process and product of social relations.

The space would be a set of objects and relations that take place on these objects; not among them specifically, but for which they serve as intermediaries. Objects help to establish a series of relationships. Space is the result of the action of human kind on their own space, intermediated by natural and artificial objects. (Santos, 2014, p. 78, my translation).

From this perspective, the notion of 'space' is produced from multiple determinations whose origin are in different levels and numerous scales, from simple places until the international dimension. Space, as mentioned in the quote above, are not only the landscape, but the localized combination of social variables. The international dimension might be understood as the process of globalization read from a Marxist perspective.

Therefore, space cannot be studied as if material objects have in themselves their determination. It must also take into consideration an object's social function and the structure that surrounds it. Each object produced is full of symbolism, meant to impose the idea of a content and a value that, in fact, it does not have. The meaning of the object is warped by appearance. To Santos (2012, p. 59), '[...] Things are already born full of symbolism, representativeness, intentionality designed to impose the idea of a content and a value that, in reality, they do not have. Its meaning is deformed by its appearance'.

The analysis, in Santos' perspective, starts from the matter itself and reaches the abstraction considering not only the individual reason, but the concrete of things. In his analyses proposal, the form introduces us to the material object, its current function guides us to the process that raised it, and the process guides us to the social structure that gives meaning to that object in a social context.

Taking a panoramic picture of the exemplary case using Santos' perspective, I might affirm that the remote education, as an object materialised in the everyday life of the students in this case, brought in its determination some socio-economic categories historically produced. I mean, remote education was not only a task that the students must accomplish to realise some grade for their course. It was also a way of life, socially determined, into which the students had to fit. This structure related to the object imposed a globalized pattern of living.

When the determination of remote education encountered the determination of the students, a fight among structures took place. At this point it was expected of the students to decide. The Students Support Service expected that this globalized way of living fitted the ongoing routine of the students. The students waited for the moment when they will have space to carry out two separate foregrounds: one during the week at the campus, the other at the weekend in their families.

Connecting this perspective based in Santos' work with a critical read provided by Skovsmose's point of view, I need to look to the dispositions of these students to try understand their engagement or non-engagement in remote classes. In this process it is necessary to consider the place where the students were, imposed on them, by the material determination, ways of meaning production and roles that must be played. This determination is historically constituted and governed by socio-economic categories. I mean, no decision taken by these students was an individual decision.

Either by the decision in itself or by the possibilities seen by the students, the totality of the social relations, materialised in the space, guided their foregrounds.

Corroborating Skovsmose (2005), what was the point in studying Mathematics when in their place, Mathematics was not for them? In other words, the foregrounds of these students had been defined by the role played by space in the mathematics education, not by their background. It is so, because the space – form, structure and content – drove these children in one way that no longer included remote education.

In the reports quoted early, Students A and B were viewing their currently space as a provisory one. The students hoped for a future where they might go back to the campus and restore their missed everyday life. This landscape is the space where education is allowed to exist, only there. But, at that moment, the space where they were, full of material determinations, guided their disposition to ways of living where such things as online meetings and scheduled activities could not exist.

Someone might say that the notion of foregrounds is sufficient to analyse the situation. To those people I will express my response as following: analyse the role played by 'space' in the determination of those foregrounds. My focus is on the space, not only in the relations that take place in the space.

At this point, I might say that the remote teaching has highlighted the difference among students. Has been also in the spot the fact of space, in Santos' terms, most be considerate. In the classroom the background of the students is easily erased, and a normative mathematics education takes place. As a sanitised landscape, the classroom imposed a globalized structure over a group of young people who live in such different spaces. During this colonizing process, these individual differences were hidden to promote equality, at least from one perspective, the colonialist perspective.

In my experience, the context of remote teaching failed to hide individual differences and mathematics education was inserted into that space. There, the normative education process is put under another set of rules; instead of dictating, it is ruled under everyday life categories.

Connections with Mathematics Education

As I note, Santos' conception of 'space' is widely acknowledged in Geography. I choose to use his approach in my first steps on the concept of 'space' because of the theoretical support it provides. But I also initiate an overview of works in Mathematics Education that have been, at some point, dealing with 'space' as a concept. This overview involves scanning some

exemplary research; it is not a state-of-the-art review. To proceed I look at some repositories guided by the keywords 'space' and 'mathematics education'. In this section I share some results of this overview.

To Martin and Larnell (2017), their perspective, on urban Mathematics Education, was raised as a response to the idea of urban as a space marked by a profound disorganization, in which mathematics education research, practice and policy are mainly concerned with reorganization of students, schools and community. That is, to these authors urban Mathematics Education goes beyond geographical context. It is imbricated into lives within its diversity in socio-cultural contexts.

In the Brazilian context there are some exemplary works. Moraes and Garnica (2016), bring an analysis of how space has been contextualized in some research, including Mathematics Education and History fields. As underlined by the authors, there are works, for example Arrais (2004), Campos (2012), and Certeau (2000), that understand space as a materialization of social relations, as well as the result of appropriations through symbolic investment that share value judgement in cities. To Moraes and Garnica (2016, p. 84), "spaces are not a neutral, they are created and creators, physical and discursive elaborations, actions and intentions. Spaces shape and are shaped by subjectivities".

Severino-Filho and Silva (2021) establish a characterization of space, based on the work of Certeau (2000), from considerations about intercultural relations that take place in teacher education spaces that work in intercultural contexts with indigenous peoples. For these authors, space is a social-cultural context that emerges from the act of inhabiting a place. Assuming this concept and theorizing about education process, the authors characterize the 'formal education space' and the 'socio-educational space'. This second one is produced by the student community and inhabited by a student at different stages of their life. In this 'socio-educational space' takes place "the different dimensions of non-school education and, consequently, the generation, acquisition, and diffusion of specific knowledge for each space" (Severino-Filho & Silva, 2021, p. 189). Regarding 'formal education space', the authors state that "our school, in its traditional structure, is a space historically reproduced, or imported, with minor adaptations, of European culture. So that the teacher's culture subdues the students' culture differences and silences their previous knowledge, believing that finally, one can replace them with standard school knowledge" (Severino-Filho & Silva, 2021, p. 190).

Inspired by Said (1990), a set of works theorises concepts directly related to the notion of 'space' – despite the fact that this word is not used as a keyword in these works. Marcone (2015) conceptualizes the notion of *deficiencialism* as a way to refer to the relation among people and space in the social context. To him, the category "disabled" people emerges from a power relation in which someone emphasises some characteristic that, in that particular context, in reference to a given pattern of humankind, another person is not able to respond as expected. In other words, the disability results from the relation with the space that these people occupy.

Bose and Marcone (2019) examine the relation among children, place and education. From the observation of a railway platform in Mumbai suburban, the authors theorise about social

justice, equity and the redefinition of young students' foregrounds. When the authors bring Skovsmose (2005) to the discussion, they throw light on some of my concerns. The authors state: "Barriers for learning are often individualised and those obstacles are considered as part of a social and cultural background attached to the person (see Skovsmose, 2005). [...] The fault, then, is on the individual and not on the system." (p. 5).

Unlike India, Brazil is not a caste-based context, but it is not out of the realm of the stratification created by capitalist social structure. When children are not allowed to play their role in this society, as in the case of the students of mine, they also have their foregrounds limited.

So, at this point of my exploration, I regard my practice as contributing to the fragmentation of the foregrounds of my students. In the previous sections of this text, I look at the remote teaching in my context from a point of view centred in the student everyday life. Here, I see it from my perspective as a teacher. Collaborating on the implementation of remote teaching and proposing activities centred in online learning or adapted to paper, I ignored a very important point of the process. In both cases, the teaching was centred in academic Mathematics and there was no place for this category in the space where my students were learning. Because of this lack of legitimacy, the everyday life of the students took over the learning process.

Highlighting this point at least two main concerns become clear: (i) the role played by education in the families; (ii) what kind of education I was proposing to my students. None of these are simple questions. None of these can be treated lightly, given the risk of falling into dichotomies or blaming families or teachers. The risk could be aligned with the discussion promoted by Skovsmose (2005) over classic and progressive racism. As in that case, I have to drive my attention to the social structure that guides the education process.

By searching for problems in the families or in the student attitudes, what remains hidden is the fact that access to education, granted by the Brazilian Constitution, has been denied to these students. I might also hypothesise that homeschooling, an education process not regulated in Brazil, has been promoted under the guise of remote education. Both of these points guide me to discuss the political implications of the questions raised in this paper. For the moment, I maintain my focus on conceptualising space and use these points to develop my research agenda.

What this brief review shows me is that the concept of 'space' has been studied from different perspectives in Mathematics Education. Some of these perspectives assume a characterization that converges to the understanding of space as a product of social practices that occurs in the relation of communities and the place where they live. This understanding seems to converge to Santos' proposal presented in the previous section of this paper.

Now, with this understanding, the question is: what can I do to get over this colonizer relation between education and space? In the following section I raise some possibilities instead of pointing to a final direction.

Forwards-looking

It is necessary to take into consideration that during the period referred to in my description of exemplary cases, I had 140 students registered in my classes. Many of them could attend the remote education without problems. I also had to deal with psychological and socio-economic issues experienced by additional students. The cases highlighted in this text, as I wrote in the subtitle, are exemplary and serve my intention of discussing the concept 'space'.

In relation to the education process it is possible to conclude that Student A and B were dealing with learning obstacles, in Skovsmose (2005) terms. To these students, remote education, unlike as expected by the institution, was not an alternative to continue their classes during the pandemic. All the options provided by the teacher and institution failed in the same point. It was not taken into consideration the social structure interlocked in the objects and places made available to students.

To build a research agenda from that experience and continue thinking about space as a philosophical concept, I raised some perspectives and questions. Bringing together the concerns of Martin and Larnell (2017), I ask: How might mathematics education in the future be even more responsive to issues of access and opportunity in the context of such forces and global urbanism? When it is clear that not everyone is able to follow together today's endeavour, like remote education and quality in the access to technology. Is it the global urbanization the only way? Should assistance policies and practices take part in this concern?

Putting space within the scope of an investigation inevitably leads us to talk about the process of colonization. Access to technology in countries like Brazil is a way of maintaining power relationships between the global north and south. Therefore, an education process mainly based in technology, poorly distributed among the society, is a strong instrument to perpetuate power relations that characterise colonizing process.

In a similar direction of Martin and Larnell (2017), my intentions in studying space and mathematics education is driven, in this moment, to the reality of Rural Education. In the same sense of these authors, I am not defining the rural space by its geographical location. So, my intention is to elaborate an approach that could be moved from Rural Education, to Intercultural Education, as in Severino-Filho and Silva (2021), without redefinitions of theorized concepts.

Seems likely that the firsts steps in this research agenda guide me to 2 key-points: It is necessary enlarge my definition of mathematics education; clearly I am addressing issues that are not included in the statement 'everyday practice of a Mathematics teacher', it may be necessary understand this practices in its material, socio-historical and political faces. The second key-point is dealing with the interrogation 'which are the implications to Mathematics Education when a researcher takes this concern in mind?'; a mathematics education concerned mainly with the standards was a cause of a fragmentation of the foregrounds of my students. Particularly, when we look to the interaction between places aligned with the global urbanization and places marginalized in this process, some

mathematics education practices corroborate to the maintenance of this power relation. Mathematics Education, as the research field that deal with these practices, is a solid ground to rise this question.

To the question “what is the relation between education and space?” a provisory answer might consider how the education process is dressed up, as pointed by Skovsmose (2005). In its current way, education hides the requirement of a normalized space. I mean, the formal education process does not only need a student and their desire to be included in this process. A globalized (and very sanitised) standard of space has been imposed within the education process. Particularly with the remote education implemented in Brazil during the pandemic, this standard promoted learning obstacles for a considerable number of students.

The theoretical support offered by Santos (2012) is seen to be suitable to this endeavour. It brings the possibility to carry out socio-economic relationships in the same time allowed for work with objects, places and landscape. At the moment this concern seems necessary to me. In the next steps, I hope to pursue in discussion in Mathematics Education and produce some possibilities and suggestions to teachers.

References

- Bose, A., & Marcone, R. (2019). Non-typical learning sites: A platform where foreground interplays with background. In J. Subramanian (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Tenth International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (pp. 274–283). MES11.
- Marcone, R. (2015). Deficiencialism: The invention of disability due to normality. [Doctoral dissertation, São Paulo State University.
- Martin, D. B., & Larnell, G. V. (2017). Urban mathematics education. In H. R. Milner & K. Lomotey (Eds.), *Handbook of urban education* (pp. 392–411). Routledge.
- Melgaço, L., & Prouse, C. (Eds.). (2017). Milton Santos: A pioneer in critical geography from the Global South. Springer.
- Santos, M. (2012). *Pensando o espaço do homem*. Editora da Universidade de São Paulo. (Original work published 1982).
- Santos, M. (2014). *Metamorfoses do espaço habitado*. Editora da Universidade de São Paulo. (Original work published 1988).
- Severino-Filho, J., & Silva, A. A. (2021). Por teorias indígenas do conhecimento: A sala de aula como espaço comunicativo transcultural. In S. M. N. Mattos, J. R. L. Mattos, & R. A. Silva (Eds.), *Interfaces educativas e cotidianas: Povos indígenas* (pp. 183–216). Editora do Instituto Federal do Amapá.
- Skovsmose, O. (2005). Foreground and politics of learning obstacles. *For the Learning of Mathematics*, 25, 4–10.